

An Empirical Study of Organizational Development through HR Services Satisfaction Index– A Case Study

(Astech. Compupowers, Pvt. Ltd)

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ABSTRACT

The ultimate objective of service index or employee satisfaction is to keep the worker happy and motivated, make him enjoy his work, have a sense of pride in the organization he belongs to and in the work he does. All this is possible through a climate where “work” and the “worker” are respected irrespective of the nature and complexity of job. The Basic objective of this HR services satisfaction index is to develop action plan to address the area of improvement regarding HR services and initiatives. The author has suggested six different attributes that are relevant to employees in their association with HR services and initiatives and also has tried to show how it helps in the organizational development with a help of a case study.

Key Words: *HR service Index, Employee Satisfaction, motivation, improved performance, organizational development.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The main common theme running across all these developmental interventions is the focus on human being rather than the job and an attempt to create a sense of meaning, satisfaction in the worker bringing out his best potential by helping him develop a sense of empowerment, of being in charge of his own destiny and creating positive relationships with people at workplace. Ultimately all this will lead to motivating the employees, improved performance and organizational development.

II. HR SERVICE INDEX

HR service satisfaction survey helps in finding out employee satisfaction level regarding the HR services provided to them. It is used as a tool to look at HR services and HR organizational environment and how it affects employee satisfaction level.

Why Employee Satisfaction?

Success comes through **people**. When companies are effective in satisfying their employees, employees stay longer; make a deeper commitment to the business, recommended ways to improve to company’s products and services and work harder to satisfy the customer.

III. REVIEW LITERATURE

In a study, **The Impact of Perceptions of Leadership Style, Use of Power, and Conflict Management Style on Organizational Outcomes** by Virginia P. Richmond, John P. Wagner, and James McCroskey, the researchers developed an instrument to measure employee satisfactions using this continuum (tell, sell, consult, join). Their research discovered that, “the supervisor who wishes to generate positive impact on satisfaction with supervision, satisfaction with work, and solidarity and to reduce communication anxiety should strive to get her/his subordinates to perceive her/him as using a more employee-entered (consult-join) leadership style.

For people and organizations who desire a model to apply, the best I have discovered was developed from work by **Tannenbaum and Schmidt (1958) and Sadler (1970)**. They provide a continuum for leadership and involvement that includes an increasing role for employees and a decreasing role for supervisors in the decision process. The continuum includes this progression.

Another social reason pointed out by the **Labor Investigation Committee** reads thus: “the provision of canteens improves the physique; entertainment reduces the incidence of vices; medical aid, maternity and child welfare services improve the health of the workers and bring down the rates of general, maternal and infantile mortality; and educational facilities increase their mental efficiency and economic productivity.

Çiğdem Kayal and Belgin Ceylan(2014) In this study; the impact of career development programs in organizations, and organizational commitment on employees' job satisfaction, and their role in increasing job satisfaction are examined. A survey is applied in a sample group working in various industries. At this point, a questionnaire that consists of two sections of 43 questions rated on a 7-point Likert attitude scale is prepared. The survey was conducted on 204 employees that work in different sectors. In the study, the data obtained from the evaluation of the survey results was interpreted by using SPSS statistics software program. Results of the analysis indicate that career development programs and organizational commitment have a partial effect on employee's job satisfaction, organizational commitment affects job satisfaction directly and positively, and career development programs in organizations do not affect the level of employee's job satisfaction. In the light of the findings arose, the results of the study are discussed and recommendations for managers as well as academics are presented.

Lumley, et al. (2011, p. 102) underline that there are nine facets of job satisfaction: pay, promotion, benefits, contingent rewards, operating procedures, supervision, co-workers, nature of the work and communication. Job satisfaction is employees' feelings concerning their jobs. Job satisfaction is hence a function of the perceived relationship between employees' anticipations in relation to the job and what they in fact gain from that job, as well as the meaning or value that employees attribute to their

jobs (Ko, 2012, p. 1005). Job satisfaction commonly expresses employees' emotional (both positive and negative) reactions towards their job (**Köroğlu, 2011, p. 248**), The common ground of the definitions of motivation in the literature is its meaning of affecting human behaviour and in the light on this effect, guiding the person towards certain actions (**Şimşek, et al., 2011**). Motivation fulfils the financial opportunities of the workers and regulates their social needs (working hours, social security, etc.). What's more, it responds to workers' need of self-realization (making decisions, taking initiatives, having the right to speak in management). Similarly, it enables to make plans that enhance the skills of the workers, increase the efficiency of the organizations and workers and, therefore, creates conditions of competition towards working in better conditions. Also, it enables the employees to display their creative thoughts and leadership skills and to benefit more from the present motivational opportunities and increases the positive competition amongst the employees. Motivation includes the increase in organization's productivity during the harmonization of the goals of the workers and the organization while conducting various methods to increase the job satisfaction that workers expect to get from the organization (**Şimşek, et al., 2011**).

IV. PROBLEM STATEMENT

There is evidence that the absence of adequate benefits and services can contribute to employee dissatisfaction and increased absenteeism and turnover. An accurate satisfaction index therefore has to work in the same way. In other words it must be weighted average satisfaction scores. **Basically, the Satisfaction Index Answers this Question:**

“How successful are we at satisfying our Employees according to the ‘n’ things that are most important to them”?

{Where n =the number of attributes on the questionnaire}

The major purpose of this research is to study the various HRD activities and their impact thereafter on its employees i.e., on their satisfaction and performance level and spirit. (These employees are MANAGEMENT and NON-MANAGEMENT employees.)

The Basic objective of HR services satisfaction survey is to develop action plan to address the area of improvement regarding HR services and initiatives the survey is based on six different attributes that are relevant to employees in their association with HR services and initiatives. And it also help us in reaching to the conclusion that how these satisfied employees will help in organizational development.

V. COMPANY PROFILE

Astech Compupower Pvt Ltd, is an sister concern of Emerson Network Power (India) Private Ltd.. It is situated near New Vidhan Sabha, Jaipur. Same work environment as in Emerson could be seen in Astech Compupower. Around two hundred employees work in Astech.

Today, they have established themselves as market leader in the Power Protection solutions and Precision Air Condition segment. Emerson Network Power India manufactures & markets Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) systems, Climate and Environmental systems, DC power systems, Automatic Transfer Switches (ATS), Racks, Monitoring Solutions and Enclosures for IT Server protection and power distribution units - all supported by world-class professional services, catering to major industries such as the IT/ITes, Telecom, Banking & Finance, Process Control, Biotech, Healthcare, Retail, Infrastructure and Government sectors.

VI. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

A major objective of Research study is to recognize and diagnose problems; here comparative analysis of different industries has been done for employee satisfaction index through satisfaction survey.

Some of the research objectives are as follows:

- Recognizing and formulating new schemes of employee satisfaction.
- Improving the existing schemes pertaining to employee satisfaction.
- Be acquainted with policies to motivate employees.
- How satisfied employees can lead to organizational development.

VII. SAMPLING METHOD

There are various sampling methods available for doing a research study. However, as far as this study is concerned CONVENIENCE SAMPLING has been opted as the best-suited method. This method goes along with this study as this method has its advantage the features of convenience and easy accessibility. Interviewing is used as a tool for a sample selection in method.

VIII. RESEARCH PROCESS

The major purpose of this research is to study the various HRD activities of ASTECH COMPUPOWER LTD. and there impact thereafter on its employees i.e., on their satisfaction and performance level and spirit. A brief overview of the research process of the present study is given below:

1. **Determining the sample design:** The universe of the study is extended to ASTECH COMPUPOWER LTD., which has employees. These employees are MANAGEMENT and NON-MANAGEMENT employees. All MGT and NON-MGT employees are from all over Rajasthan, Jaipur. 70 out of 100 are non mgt employees and 30 are mgt employees.
2. **Collection of data:** The data was collected through questionnaire and interview method secondary data were gathered with the help of journals, books, proceedings and other published materials of the HR POLICY, ASTECH COMPUPOWER LTD.
3. **Analysis of data:** The data so collected were thoroughly analyzed. They have been codified and tabulated. Relevant satisfaction relationships have been established and analyzed. The analysis of data gave rise to various findings and suggestions.
4. **Interpretation of data:** The data has been interpreted to arrive at some concrete conclusion. Various statistical methods, formulations, and techniques have been applied for the interpretation of data.

SIX DIFFERENT ATTRIBUTES are: -

1. HR DEPARTMENT AND HR POLICES

➤ **THE HIGH-PERFORMANCE WORK SYSTEM**
The HPWS is a set of HR policies and practices that maximize the competencies, commitment, and abilities of the firm's employees. In practice, this

means that each HPWS HR activity produces measurable superior results. The evidence suggests that “high performance HR practices, [particularly] combined with new technology, produce better productivity, quality, sales, and financial performance”

➤ **TRANSLATING STRATEGY INTO HR POLICY AND PRACTICE**

The HR manager needs a way to translate the firm’s new strategy onto specific, actionable Hr policies and practices. Management formulates a strategic plan. That strategic plan implies certain workforce requirements, in terms of the employee skills, attributes, and behaviors that HR must deliver to enable the business to achieve its strategic goals.

➤ **CREATING A STRATEGY-ORIENTED HR SYSTEM (DEPARTMENT)**

We can think of an HR process as consisting of three basic components. There are the HR **professionals** who have the strategic and other skills required to build a strategy-oriented HR system. There are the HR **polices** and **activities** (such as how the company recruits, selects, and trains and rewards employees) that comprise the HR system itself. Some HR experts refer to these three elements (the HR professionals, the HR system, and the resulting employee behaviours) as a company’s basic HR architecture (see figure)

Ideally, the HR professionals should deign the HR system in such a way that it helps to produce the employee competencies and behaviours the company needs to achieve its strategic goals. The HR professional has to understand how businesses operate.

SERVICE PROFIT CHAIN

- The Power Of Recognition
- Reward System
- The Fun Factor- A Big Element Of Your Business Strategy
- Coaching

The desired workforce skills, attributes, and behaviours. (These may take the form of new selection, training, and compensation policies and practices, for instance.) Ideally, HR management initiatives are supporting management’s strategic goals.

2. WELFARE SCHEMES AND FACILITIES

➤ **TYPES OF WELFARE FACILITIES**

Welfare services may broadly be classified into two categories (1) Instrumental activities which are provided within the establishment such as urinals, crèches, rest centers, canteens, uniforms, library, medical aid, subsidized food, shift allowance etc; (2) Extramural activities which are undertaken outside the establishment such as family planning, child welfare, cooperative stores, credit societies, vocational guidance, holiday homes, leave travel facilities, housing, transport to and from the place of work etc.

Labor welfare work may also be divided into two categories: (1) statutory welfare work comprising the legal provisions in various, pieces of labour legislation (2) Voluntary welfare work includes those activities which are undertaken by employers for their workers voluntarily. Many employers, nowadays, offer the following welfare amenities voluntarily:

- Housing
- Transportation
- Education

- **Other facilities:** Other amenities such as washing facilities, drinking water, provision of first aid box, rest rooms, canteen, recreation centers, have, more or less, become statutory obligations of employers nowadays.

3. WORKING CONDITIONS AND HRS

HR manger must frame the working hrs and condition in such a manner so that employees get a solution to meet the problem of fractionated, boring, and programmed work, at an acceptable price, with undiminished quality and quantity of product for this manager take help of many approaches toward increasing worker’s freedom and their motivation they can feel good about themselves as well as organization and can increase their productivity. Those approaches are as under:-

- **WORK MODULE**

The benefits of work modules lie in increasing diversity for the employees, by dividing up and sharing the undesirable work activities, expanding work independence to the bottom of the hierarchy, and constructing the job to meet the needs of the individual, rather than forcing people to fit a particularly defined job.

- **APPROACHES TO IMPROVE QWL**

There are a number of factors involved in QWL, and these factors can be grouped in three categories: individual factors, job factors, and organizational factors. The characteristics of these factors affect the individual involvement in the job, his sense of competence which leads to job satisfaction and finally to job performance and productivity as shown in figure

- **QUALITY OF WORK LIFE**

It is, concerned with the overall climate of the work. The basic purpose of improving QWL is to change the climate at work so that human-technological-organizational interface leads to a better quality of work life.

4. CARRER DEVELOPMWENT

For our purposes, we will define **career** as “a sequence of positions occupied by a person during the **competence** course of a lifetime.” Therefore, any work, paid or unpaid, pursued over an extended period of time, can constitute a career. In addition to formal job work, it may include schoolwork, homemaking, or volunteer work.

- **INDIVIDUAL VERSUS ORGANIZATIONAL PERSPECTIVE**

From an organization or managerial standpoint, career development involves tracking career paths. Management seeks information so it can direct and monitor the progress of minorities and women, and to ensure capable managerial and technical talent will be available to meet the organization’s needs.

- **CAREER STAGES**

We will propose a five stages model that is generalizable to most people during their adult years, regardless of the type of work they do. We identify five career stages that most of us have gone through or will go through during these years: exploration, establishment, and mid-career, late career, and decline.

More specifically, we can identify several positive results that can accrue from a well-designed career development:

1. Ensures Needed Talent Will Be Available:
2. Improves the Organization’s Ability to attract and Retain High-Talent Personnel: -
3. Ensures That Minorities and Women Get Opportunities for Growth and Development
4. Reduces Employee Frustration

5. EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION

The Logic behind employee participation is quite simple: by involving workers in those divisions that affect them and by increasing their autonomy and control over their work lives, employees will become

more motivated, more committed to the organization, more productive and more satisfied with their jobs.

Since they are treated with respect now, they begin to view the job and the organization as their own and commit themselves to organizational activities wholeheartedly. Bilateral

The major objectives of the scheme of worker’ participation is:

- To improve the quality of working life
- To secure the mutual cooperation of employees and employers in achieving industrial peace; greater efficiency and productivity in the interest of the enterprise, the workers, the consumers and the nation.

Decisions help in bringing out radical changes in organizational system, plans and procedures more easily. Employees do not feel threatened by such moves, as they understand and appreciate the reasons behind such ‘strategic shifts’

6. ORGANIZATION CLIMATE AND CULTURE

The Organization climate and culture’s objectives and strategies for the future determine future human resources needs. That is, the number and mix of human resources are a reaction to the overall organizational strategy.

➤ **CLIMATE OF ORGANIZATION**

Organization is also referred to in the context of climate, which prescribes the relationships among individuals, and positions that they hold. There may be different ways in which these relationships are prescribed. Climate tends to be somewhat permanent with a provision of incorporating

➤ **ORGANIZATION AS CULTURE**

Organizational culture refers to a system of shared meaning held by members that distinguishes the organization from other organizations. This system of shared meaning is, on closer examination, a set of key characteristics that the organization values. The research suggests that there are seven primary characteristics that, in aggregate, capture the essence of an organization’s culture.

In contrast, Employee satisfaction seeks to measure affective responses to the work environment. It’s concerned with how employees feel about the

organization’s expectations, reward practices, and the like. Although the two terms undoubtedly have overlapping characteristics, keep in mind that the term **Organizational culture** is descriptive, while employee satisfaction is evaluative.

1. Innovation and risk taking. The degree to which employees are encouraged to be innovative and take risks.

2. Attention to detail: The degree to which employees are expected to exhibit precision, analysis, and attention to detail.

3. Outcome Orientation: The degree to which management focuses on results or outcomes rather on the techniques and process used to achieve those outcomes

4. People Orientation: The degree to which management decision take into consideration the effect of outcomes on people within the organization

5. Team orientation: The degree to which work activities are organized around teams rather than individuals human resources planning.

6. Aggressiveness: The degree to which people are aggressive and competitive rather than easygoing

7. Stability: The degree to which organizational activities emphasize maintaining the status quo in contrast to growth.

Each of these characteristics exists on a continuum from low to high. Appraising the organization on these seven characteristics, then, gives a composite picture of the organization’s culture.

IX. FINDING AND ANALYSIS

SATISFACTION FOR EMPLOYEE:

These research discovered that, “the supervisor who wishes to generate positive impact on satisfaction with supervision, satisfaction with work, and solidarity and to reduce communication anxiety should strive to get her/his subordinates to perceive her/him as using a more employee-centred (consult-join) leadership style.” At the same time, however, employees cannot see the supervisor as abdicating responsibility for decision-making and it is Useful when communicating about safety issues, government regulations, and decisions and to ask for employee their needs and their problems in the organization.

The employer should solve their (employees) problem and provide them various facilities like E.g.: providing them loan, various career opportunities, etc. And employer must show best talent within an organization should be made insular to the external world so that the loyalty or productive employee is ensured on a continuous basis to an organization. And employees feel secure their organization and increase their productivity.

1. HR DEPARTMENT AND ITS POLICES

Employees	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
MGT. Employees	1	8	85	6
Non MGT. Employees	1	12	80	7

2. WELFARE SCHEME AND FACILITIES

Employees	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
MGT. Employees	1	10	80	9
Non MGT. Employees	1	10	82	5

3. WORKING HRS & CONDITIONS

Employees	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
MGT. Employees	3	5	87	5
Non MGT. Employees	5	10	80	5

4. CARRER DEVELOPMENT

Employees	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
MGT. Employees	1	8	85	6
Non MGT. Employees	1	11	80	8

5. EMPLOYEE PARTICIPATION

Employees	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
MGT. Employees	1	7	87	5
Non MGT. Employees	1	10	82	7

X. WORK CULTURE

Astech Compupower Pvt. ltd. invites people to an organization with **no boundaries**, a workplace activated by opportunities and challenges leading to high levels of excellence through innovation and empowerment. They are looking at high performing leaders, future oriented, innovative and proactive individuals. A self-starter who has the ability to harmonize individual development with the Organization goals and objectives with the right spirit. They must be committed to their task and have an urge for continuous learning with humility of mind together with honesty and integrity in their dealings coupled with trust in their relationship.

They put **people** first as we believe they are the drivers of the organization. At Emerson Network Power we've always endowed outstanding professionals, and have maintained that it is our people who deliver what the customers need.

Some of their benefits include...

- An Open Culture
- A Learning Environment and on the Job Learning
- Performance based Compensation
- Employee care / benefits

THE MANAGEMENT POLICY

EQUAL OPPORTUNITY TO all employees

Equal employment opportunity policy assures that there will be no discrimination or harassment against an employee or applicant on the grounds of race, color, religion, sex, age, disability, national origin, or any other factor considered unlawful by applicable laws and regulation.

THE MANAGEMENT PROCESS

Astech Compupower Pvt Ltd, management subscribes to the principle that "When people understand the process and are part of it, you can do anything." To that end, Astech makes sure that

employees understand the fundamentals of its management process in the following principles:

1) Keep it simple

- Set tough targets
- Develop detailed plans and programs
- Follow up on implementation and pay for results

2) Commitment to planning

- Identify and evaluate opportunities for investment that are essential for growth
- Planning must culminate in significant actions with measurable results

3) Strong system of follow-up and control

- Crucial action in implementing plans successfully

4) Action-oriented organization

- Taking action is closely associated with the level at which profits are planned and controlled, which is the
- lowest applicable level in the organization

5) Operational Excellence

- Emerson's goal is to be the highest quality manufacturer with the lowest relative costs in the world

6) An operating environment where people can and do make a difference Management leadership is the key factor in making this principle a reality on a daily basis

XI. ANALYSIS OF THE STUDY

11.1 HR Service Satisfaction Survey

Employee Satisfaction Survey Solution Driving Employee loyalty

Research shows that satisfied, motivated employees will create higher customer satisfaction and in turn positively influence organizational performance. Noticing this trend, many organizations are investing in measuring and quantifying employee opinions and attitudes by incorporating Employee Satisfaction Survey into their existing HR and organizational processes. By establishing frequent and consistent employee feedback processes, Confirmed solutions enable enterprises to retain and develop their most vital asset: employees.

MORE ACCURATE PERSPECTIVE

Organizations achieve a more accurate view of current policies and a more clear perspective of issues that are of higher priority to employees than others, such as benefits versus career development, versus compensation.

INCREASED EMPLOYEE LOYALTY

By quantifying and analyzing employee attitudes and opinions, enterprises can identify problem areas and solutions to create a supportive work environment encouraging a motivated and loyal workforce.

EMPLOYEE INVOLVEMENT

Employee involvement is creating an environment in which people have an impact on decisions and actions that affect their jobs. Employee involvement is not the goal nor is it a tool, as practiced in many organizations. Rather, it is a management and leadership philosophy about how people are most enabled to contribute to continuous improvement and the ongoing success of their work organization. Working with people for 40+ years, is to involve people as much as possible in all aspects of work decisions and planning. This involvement increases ownership and commitment, retains your best employees, and fosters an environment in which people choose to be motivated and contributing.

How to involve employees in decision making and continuous improvement activities is the strategic aspect of involvement and can include such methods as suggestion systems, manufacturing cells, work teams, continuous improvement meetings, Kaizen (continuous improvement) events, corrective action processes, and periodic discussions with the supervisor. Intrinsic to most employee involvement processes is training in team effectiveness, communication, and problem solving; the development of reward and recognition systems; and frequently, the sharing of gains made through employee involvement efforts

XII. SUGGESTED DEVELOPMENT PLAN FOR EMPLOYEES

The development plan for workers could focus on the following areas of development:

- **Work Improvements and Skill Development:** - Development needs through work improvements

could be plan through in-company skill training, quality circle, job-rotation, multi-skills training and other such methods. These methods are not being elaborated as they are fairly well-known and well practiced.

- **Personal Growth and Motivation Management:** - In recent years a few organizations have attempted to conduct personal growth workshops and camps for workers. Such personal growth laboratories are quit common for manager.
- **Family and Social Responsibilities:** - Another important area of development of Indian workers is their role in relation to their family, and to the development of he family members themselves. Executives can take care of the development of their family members as they belong to relatively upper classes of the society. HRD for workers should include HRD for the family. It is useful for organization to think of creating development opportunities for the family members of the workers. Providing educational facilities for the children, special guidance and counselling centres', personality development programs, cultural development opportunities, etc. are mechanisms of motivation development and integration into the organization.
- **Values and Attitude Development:** - As in the case of personal growth it is useful to organize special programs for developing the right kind of values and attitudes in the employees. This can be done through specially organized "value camps" or "attitude development" programs.

XIII. CONCLUSION

A healthy employer attitude towards its people cannot by itself attract, but also motivate high performing employees. Other steps must follow. Without this crucial foundation, however, all other efforts will eventually crumble. A strong work force is not an act of fate. It is built and nurtured by the attitudes of the people within it. As we know that Human relation are the medium through which both employees and the company mutually cooperate for the maximum cooperate for the maximum satisfaction of the economic social and psychological wants of the people having relation with an organization which has the objective of increasing productivity.

- We may conclude by saying that an happy employee is satisfied employee. There are different attributes of HR service in an

organization to measure the satisfaction levels of an employee. These satisfied employees then gets motivated and work more efficiently and effectively in the organization. Thus, finally leading to organizational commitment

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